

Network of Inclusive COVEs on Circular Material Welding and Preventive Maintenance for Socially Safe, Resilient & Sustainable Automotive Manufacturing

D1.2 Data Management Plan

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Erasmus+ Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101193814

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